

PERSONALITY-BASED COUNSELING AND OJT PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS AT BULACAN STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship of personality of 166 college students from the College of Information Technology and Business Administration (CITBA) and College of Industrial Technology (CIT) of Bulacan State University, Bustos Campus, regarding the performance in the On-the-Job training. This study also attempted to ascertain the effect of personality-based counseling intervention on the same 166 college students with their work performance in the OJT. Through random sampling, out of 684 students enrolled in CIT and CITBA, 166 were used as the sample in this study, and 11.8% came from CITBA. 12.6% came from CIT, with ages ranging from 17 to 32, from which 68.3% comprised of males, 31.7% comprised of females, and 40.7% of them counseled, 59.3% uncounseled. The Kruskal-Wallis H test shows no statistically significant relationship between the Personality Profile and the age of the respondents, since $p > 0.05$, in all personality profiles. The Kruskal-Wallis H test also shows no statistically significant relationship between the personality and the sex of the respondents since $p > 0.05$. But A Kruskal-Wallis H test shows a statistically significant relationship between the respondents' personality profile and courses since $p > 0.05$. Pearson Correlation Coefficient tested the relationship between OJT performance and their personality profile. A statistically significant relationship between the OJT performance and their personality profile since $p > 0.05$. A set of recommendations was formulated based on the results to increase the relevance of the university's counseling intervention program in the OJT performance of the students.

Keywords: Personality, Counseling, and OJT Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

College students are social beings. In one way or another, they need the help and guidance of others. Parents, grandparents, teachers, other elders, home, school, and society guide the youngsters for successful living. Our present-day society needs professional guidance due to the explosion of knowledge, industrialization, and changes in socio-economic settings.

As an integral part of education, guidance and counseling helps in achieving the goals and objectives of education. As stated in Republic Act 9258, or the Guidance and Counselling Act of 2004, guidance and counseling in the Philippines should be regarded as an integral part of education and not as a special, psychological, or social service which is supplementary to educational purposes. Generally, guidance and counseling is for all students, not just only for those who deviate from the norm in one direction or the other.

In line with this, the Bulacan State University (BulSU) established its Guidance and Counselling Services Centers at the main campus in the City of Malolos, Bulacan, and its satellite campuses in the municipalities of Matungao, Bulakan, Hagonoy, Bustos, and in the City of San Jose Del Monte.

The main purpose of the Guidance and Counselling Services Centers (GCSC) is to assist individuals in decision-making, particularly cultivating the gradual development of the ability in making the right choices in life independently and without being unduly influenced by others. Moreover, these GCSCs promote the academic and personal success of the students by

providing emotional and psychological care in dealing with their personal and emotional problems. One of the services provided by the GCSCs is the proper assignment of On-The-Job-Training (OJT) students.

In consonance with the Commission on Higher Education's (CHED) Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 104, S. 2017, BulSU instituted an effective academic Student Internship Program (SIP), by establishing strong academic linkages with business and industry partners and with duly recognized government and non-government organizations (GOs & NGOs). Academic internships link theory and practice in supervised and scheduled work. These internship programs not only improve students' skills but also polish their professional growth and experience. Through academic internship programs, students can be facilitated to better implement their concepts in the workplace. Ylagan (2013) stated that on-the-job training is one of the mechanics of Higher Education industries in developing the needed competencies of its graduates. Its goals and objectives served as a guide in developing the needed competencies for a particular job and translating the training into a gainful working experience.

During the internship program, students may encounter some problems that may affect their performance. At the beginning of the internship program, students expect the instructors to support them theoretically in terms of counseling, practice skills, and psychological support.

To ensure the positive progress of the maritime students of Lyceum of the Philippines University (LPU), Batangas, Duran, et al. (2015) reported that the academic development, spiritual development, and character formation interventions rendered by the Counselling and Testing Center of LPU were effective. They recommended that the implementation of interventions and services be continued to ensure the positive progress of the students. They also recommended that more effective interventions be formulated and managed to respond to the counseling needs of more students. In the same way, Calaguas' (2012) study revealed the importance of assessing students' capabilities for admissions, and placements and providing better guidance and counseling programs at Pampanga State Agricultural University.

However, there is no guarantee that after the SIP, students could address the demand of employers such as communication skills, interpersonal skills, and financial literacy with professional work ethics. Although work performance ratings in OJT are given by GOs, NGOs, businesses, and industry partners, no studies have been conducted so far on OJT students' personality profiles and OJT Performance of Students.

To ensure the achievement of the SIP of the University, the Guidance, and Counselling Services Centers administer OMNI Personality Inventory to students who would undergo (SIP) and analyze their work performance as assessed by business or industry OJT partners. The study assumed that if the students already had the right mindset toward their career, they could consciously apply or take into consideration the pieces of advice given to them at the time of counseling.

On the other hand, if the students had the wrong self-concept as revealed by their personality test, the corresponding counseling interventions could correct or help them modify their wrong perspectives. Either combined or undertaken individually, the intervention could assist the students in reaching their desired level of outcome for themselves.

The prior studies have stressed the value of counseling intervention in the school performance of learners in the classroom and even in a workplace set-up. However, no studies have been undertaken so far on the personality profile and OJT performance of students at BulSU or in other higher education institutions in the Philippines.

This serves as a rationale for the conduct of this study.

Problem Statement

This study aimed to determine the relationship between personality profile and the OJT performance of graduating students from the College of Information Technology and Business Administration (CITBA), and College of Industrial Technology (CIT) of BulSU Bustos Campus during the school year 2018-2019.

Research Questions

1. What is the personal profile of OJT students at Bulacan State University in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 sex
 - 1.3 course?

2. What is the personality profile of OJT students in terms of the following traits:
 - 2.1 Agreeableness,
 - 2.2 Conscientiousness,
 - 2.3 Extraversion,
 - 2.4 Narcissism,
 - 2.5 Neuroticism,
 - 2.6 Openness, and
 - 2.7 Sensation-seeking?
3. What is the OJT performance level of the students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the student's personality and their age, sex, and course?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the student's personality and their OJT work performance level?
6. Is there a significant relationship between counseling interventions and OJT work performance?
7. What are the recommendations to further improve the relevance of the university's counselling program in improving the OJT performance of students?

Hypotheses

The study tested the following null hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between the students' personality and their ages, sexes, and courses.
2. There is no significant relationship between the students' personality and their OJT work performance level.
3. There is no significant relationship between counseling interventions and OJT work performance.

Scope and Delimitation

The study examined the personality profile and OJT performance of 166 graduating students from two colleges of BulSU Bustos Campus, namely: The College of Information Technology and Business Administration (CITBA), and the College of Industrial Technology (CIT) during SY 2018-2019. The personality profile of the student respondents was focused on seven factors, namely: Agreeableness; Conscientiousness; Extraversion; Narcissism; Neuroticism; Openness; and Sensation-seeking.

The performance appraisal forms submitted to BulSU by business and industry partners served as the basis of the students' OJT performance. The student's OJT performance was assessed as regards: teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity, initiative, dependability, attitude, and professionalism.

Regarding the respondents' profile, the study delimited it to age, sex, and course. Stratified random sampling was used in selecting the respondents in this study.

Significance of the Study

The results of the research may provide CHED an adequate basis for issuing orders that will help intern students in improving their performance and work behavior in doing their OJT. In addition, the personality test results can be maximized in favor of the test takers and the OJT host training partners, eventually generating a relevant policy that will be national in the application.

It will give parameters to OJT supervisors in coaching and mentoring student interns before and during their deployment.

The results of this study may provide insights to school administrators in formulating rules and policies to improve the Guidance and Counselling Services of the Student Affairs and Services department. Particularly, this may lead to policy recommendations to institutionalize personality-based counseling to all OJT college students after they have been given psychological tests as part of their requirements before deployment to their respective workplaces.

The results of the study may also help the dean and faculty of the College of Information Technology and Business Administration, and the College of Industrial Technology in establishing more objective criteria for selecting incoming students, which also includes non-cognitive factors such as personality.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Personality

Personality is a collection of intrinsic and extrinsic traits that may affect an individual's behavior. So, the evaluation of someone's personality, character traits, or characteristics plays the primary role (Allport, 1937).

On the other hand, Long (2005) refers to the word 'personality' as a pattern of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that make everyone who she or he is. People do not always think, feel, and behave in the same way – it depends on the situation they are in, the people with them, and many other things. But mostly, they tend to behave in predictable ways or patterns. And so, they can be described as shy, selfish, lively, and so on. Everyone has a set of these patterns, and this set makes up the personality. He said that personality does not change very much, but it does develop as people go through different experiences in life, and as their circumstances change. So, as people mature with time, their thinking, feelings, and behavior all change. They are usually flexible enough to learn from past experiences and to change their behavior to cope with life more effectively.

Dimensions of Personality

These so-called Big Five dimensions namely: (1) extraversion refers to the level of comfortability with relationships to others. It represents personality characteristics as active, assertive, talkative, outgoing, social, gregarious, energetic, and ambitious. These people are good at active communication and full of positive energy (Barrick and Mount, 1991; Goldberg, 1990; Watson and Clark, 1997); (2) agreeableness refers to the degree to which an individual differs from others. This trait represents personality characteristics as cooperative, soft-hearted, tolerant, forgiving, altruistic, emotionally supportive, courteous, good-natured, flexible, and self-sacrifice (Barrick and Mount, 1991; Digman, 1990); (3) conscientiousness refers to the degree to which an individual is reliable. It represents different sub traits as organized, dependable, responsible, conformity, orderly, diligent, vigilant, attentive, cautious, logical, risk averter, systematized, thorough, comprehensive, reliable, determined and keep focused on their goal for achieving success (Digman, 1990; Barrick and Mount, 1991); (4) neuroticism refers to the low level of emotional stability. Costa and McCrae (1992) define neuroticism in the following words "Neuroticism signifies variances of an individual tendency to experience suffering and is defined as emotionally insecure and uneven" and (5) openness as a personality trait refers to the degree or level of one's imagination or fascination. It represents personality characteristics such as curiosity, novelty, cultivation, aesthetic, sensitivity, independent-minded, intellectual, and creativity (Barrick and Mount, 1991; Goldberg, 1990; Digman, 1990).

This means that someone's personality is a combination of the said dimensions. These are not "types" of personalities, but *dimensions* of personality. So, someone's personality is the combination of each of their Big Five personality characteristics. For example, someone may be hardworking (high conscientiousness) but can be easily stressed or with a low level of stability. The low level of emotional stability, in return, can oppose the good level of conscientiousness of a person. He or she can be at risk for anxiety while performing a task and therefore lose the sense of being hardworking.

Domains of Personality and Temperament

Since personality traits predict consequential outcomes, it is crucial that a closer look at personality processes is likewise being done. Personality processes are mechanisms that unfold over time to produce the effects of personality traits. Personality and its consequential outcomes are evident in the research of Hampson (2012) who puts forward three broad domains of personality and temperament.

Extraversion is closely aligned with the temperament of positive emotionality or positive affect (Clark & Watson, 2008; John et al., 2008; Rothbart 2011) and emerges as a broad dimension in all descriptions of personality structure. Extraversion-introversion contrasts people who are described as sociable, energetic, and assertive with ones who are reserved, withdrawn, and submissive (Eysenck & Eysenck, 1985).

Neuroticism and anger are closely aligned with the temperament of negative emotionality (Clark & Watson, 2008; John et al., 2008; Rothbart 2011) and with the neurological Behavioral Inhibition System or BIS (Gray, 1987; Gray & McNaughton, 2000). In contrast to those who are emotionally stable, more neurotic individuals are prone to be worried, anxious, moody, irritable, and depressed (Costa & McCrae, 1992; John & Srivastava, 1999).

The trait of conscientiousness describes individual differences in adhering to socially prescribed rules and norms for impulse control, in being task- and goal-directed, and able to delay gratification. At the extremes, the conscientiousness dimension distinguishes people who are orderly, industrious, and prudent from those who are undisciplined, lazy, and unreliable.

Personality Disorders

If you have a personality disorder, you may find that your beliefs and attitudes are different from most other people. They may find your behavior unusual or unexpected and may find it difficult to spend time with you. This proves that people with personality disorders could end up with persistent pervasive abnormality in social relationships and functioning (Gask, Evans & Kessler, 2013). Personality disorders are a diagnostic category of psychiatric disorders that affect approximately 10 percent of the population (Torgersen, 2005). Since everyone has a personality, but not everyone has a personality disorder, these disorders are considered a variant form of a normal, healthy personality. The exact cause of personality disorders remains uncertain. However, there are both biological and psychosocial factors that influence the development of personality and personality disorders (APA, 1952).

In a study done by the Economic and Social Research Council in the United Kingdom (ESRC, 2009), it was found that anxious individuals take a hard time avoiding distractions and take a longer time to turn their attention from one task to the next compared to their less anxious peers. It concluded that anxiety may not always be obvious but then it has a hidden cause on academic performance. Similarly, Bornstein's (2005) study showed that when dependent personality traits become rigid and inflexible, they can have myriad negative effects on social and occupational functioning. When the dependency is both intense and pervasive, adversely affecting many different aspects of a person's life, it may indicate the presence of dependent personality disorder.

Theories on Personality

Both counseling and theories of learning recognize that every student has a unique personality and different set of behaviors that can influence his or her performance in school and the workplace context.

Work Context

This is illustrated in the study done by Awadh (2010) in the Saudi Arabian work context. The study reveals that personality traits and work-related attitudes such as job involvement and organizational commitment have direct positive significant relationships with employee's work performance, with the moderating effect of organizational culture.

Career expert Richard Bolles (2014) states that all people have hundreds of skills and typically use some but not all at any given time. They tend to be familiar with their "motivated skills" (the skills they love using), but they also have other, less known, strengths

School Context

Utilizing the Big Five Personality Factors (Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, Neuroticism) and the student's GPA (Grade Point Average), Hakimi et.al, (2011), were able to establish a significant relationship between personality traits with academic achievement. Also, they found that personality characteristics accounted for 48 percent of the variance in academic achievement, and among all the predictors of academic achievement, conscientiousness was the strongest.

Comparably, regarding predictors of academic performance of secondary school students, Akomolafe's (2013) study reveals that personality dimension jointly and relatively predicts academic performance, except for neuroticism. The findings imply that teachers should construct learning environments that take into consideration students' differences and strengths.

Personality Theories

Erikson's Psychosocial Theory

Psychosocial theory claims that there are eight stages that everyone must pass through. Among the eight stages, the most important developmental task to solve in psychosocial development is identity versus role confusion. In the identity theory developed by Stryker (1968; as cited in Adamson & Pasley, 2013), identity focuses on the individual's integration of societal expectations regarding the meaning of occupying particular social positions or statuses (e. g., parent, spouse, employee) and the behavioral expectations associated with such statuses. Furthermore, Erikson (1968) considered identity as the

fundamental organizing principle which develops constantly throughout the lifespan. He also believed that a positively solved identity versus role confusion crisis enables the person to integrate self-perception images into a stable personal identity, as well as strengthen the performance of different roles and achieve commitments. Thus, an unresolved crisis of a person during the primary and secondary years of schooling can lead to critical cases.

Sigmund Freud's Psychoanalytic Theory. Sigmund Freud was the first psychoanalyst and a true pioneer in the recognition of the importance of unconscious mental activity (Beystehner, 1998). He viewed that the structure of personality is divided into three aspects, the id, the ego, and the superego. The id is the instinctual part of the mind in which people are driven by pleasure while the superego represents the moral conscience, and the ego is the part of the mind which has been altered by the direct influence of the external environment. According to Corey (1986), Freud gave psychology a new look and new horizons. He called attention to psychodynamic factors that motivate behavior, focused on the role of the unconscious, and developed most of the first therapeutic procedures for understanding and modifying the structure of one's basic character.

In every aspect of human personality, psychoanalytic theory views tension, conflict, and anxiety are unavoidable. In this sense, through counseling, those conflicts in personality are expected to be reduced. The conflict in personality manifests in all people, thus all will benefit from counseling. The goals of psychoanalytic theory, according to Wadsworth (1990), aimed to provide a climate that helps clients re-experience early family relationships and uncover buried feelings associated with past events that carry over into current behavior as well as to facilitate insight into the origins of faulty psychological development, and to stimulate a corrective emotional experience.

School Counseling

The birth of what is now school counseling began in response to the sweeping societal changes and educational reforms set in motion in the late 1800s by the Industrial Revolution, which had shifted many people from farms to factories (Gysbers & Henderson, 2001). Vocational guidance in schools helped students respond to that shift by helping them in the transition from school to the workplace (Lambie & Williamson, 2004; Parsons, 1909). School counseling has now moved away from the question "What do school counselors do?" towards asking "How have students benefited because of what school counselors do?" (ASCA, 2005).

Dekruyf, Auger & Trice-Black (2011) claimed that there is a need to integrate counseling into the roles of educational leaders and mental health professionals. This was realized based on the unmet mental needs of students, unmet referrals, replaced the role of counselors by other mental health providers in school, the potentiality of losing the unique role of counselor, and the natural link between the role of the mental health professional and the wide social factors that contribute to student achievement. It was believed that school counselors are an important part of the educational leadership team and provide valuable assistance to students regardless of whether they work in an elementary school or middle school, high school, or beyond.

Similarly, different forms of counseling have been found to bring positive effects in different learning areas. Small group counseling intervention was considered impactful in the significant improvement of ninth- and tenth-grade underachieving students in the areas of organizational skills, time management, and motivation (Berger, 2013) and students enrolled in an academically rigorous program were able to persevere and succeed when given counseling-intensive support (Tovar, 2014).

When investigated in a workplace context, Ekpang (2015) in her research entitled "Counselling for Effective Work Performance: A Way for Service Improvement", asserts that in a situation where employees fail to be productive because of a personal problem, counseling service is a tool to improve their performance. She concludes that for work organizations to be productive, workplace counseling should be organized for employees whose work performances have declined because of personal problems.

Learning and Counseling Theories

Counseling intervention is carried out with guidance or under the perspective of well-established theories on learning.

The constructivist Theory of Learning

This theory does not believe in dictating to your clients what to do, instead, it views teaching as a scaffold or a guide for better decisions and that learning is the active construction of knowledge. It originated in the works of Piaget, Bruner, and Vygotsky.

According to Piaget (1955), there are three mechanisms in which a person engages in making their knowledge namely: assimilation (receiving new facts or responding to the new situation in conformity with the existing mental structure), accommodation (modifying the current schema because of new experience) and equilibrium (seeking sound mental health through assimilation and accommodation). Within these three mechanisms, the guidance counselor of an institution is of great help to students.

Lev Vygotsky (1962) also made a significant contribution to this theory. He claimed that there is a difference between what the child can do on his own and what can be accomplished with some assistance called a zone of proximal development (ZPD). Vygotsky believed that when a student is in ZPD for a particular task, providing the appropriate assistance will give the student enough of a "boost" to achieve the task. Moreover, skills too difficult for a child to master on his or her can be done with guidance and encouragement from a knowledgeable person (McLeod, 2012). Helping the child to reach the ZPD refers to scaffolding in which support was given to the students based on their needs with the intention of helping them achieve their learning goals.

Mark Tappan (1998) proposed the following four-component model that the teacher can use to optimize their scaffolding efforts and to help students move through their ZPD: (1) model desired academic behavior; (2) create a dialogue with the students; (3) practice and (4) confirmation. The "confirmation" process is one of the most important in Tappan's works in which it is stated that confirming others about bringing out the best in them by focusing on what they can do if given some assistance. In the same manner, counselors always try a healthy dialogue with their clients, and they practice confirmation mostly through positive verbal adjectives or reasons.

Behavioral Theory of Learning

For the aspect of realizing the great significance of counseling in every single student at the university, a theory can be reflected upon is the Behavioral Theory of learning. This theory was popularized by Pavlov, Watson, Thorndike, and Skinner. Skinner is the one who introduced the stimulus-response theory and the term 'operant' which means to act upon (Reyes and Dizon, 2005). The basic idea behind operant conditioning is that all behaviors are accompanied by certain consequences and these consequences strongly influence whether these behaviors are repeated and at what level of intensity (Snowman and Biehler, 2006).

Counseling can be a form of reward or positive reinforcement to students for them to have a quality performance since reward does not only pertain to material things. It can also be a simple verbal appreciation. In behavioral therapy, counselors utilizing behavioral theory assume that the client's behavior is the result of conditioning. The counselor further assumes that everyone behaves predictably to any given situation or stimulus, depending on what has been learned (Ivey and Ivey, 1993). Gilliland, James, and Bowman (1989) pointed out that modern counseling involves the client in the analysis, planning, process, and evaluation of his or her behavior management program. The counselor is expected to have training and experience in human behavior modification and to serve as a consultant, teacher, adviser, reinforcer, and facilitator. The theory helps group members eliminate maladaptive behaviors and learn new more effective behavioral patterns.

Rational Emotive Therapy (RET)

This theory assumes that people can act in either a rational or irrational manner. Rational behavior is viewed as effective and potentially productive whereas irrational behavior results in unhappiness and non-productivity. Albert Ellis as quoted by Enfield (2010) assumed that many types of emotional problems result from irrational patterns of thinking. This irrational pattern may begin early in life and be reinforced by significant events in the individual's life as well as by the general culture and environment.

The RET approach to counseling declares that most people in our society have developed many irrational ways of thinking and that these irrational thoughts lead to irrational or inappropriate behavior. Counseling is designed to help people recognize and change these irrational beliefs into more rational ones. The accomplishment of this goal requires an active, confronting, and authoritative counselor who can utilize a whole variety of techniques (Hansen, et al., 1986).

Client-centered Therapy.

Carl Rogers is a psychotherapist who believed that the client is the most important person and so he developed client-centered therapy. The therapist is not the one to tell the client what to do but rather the client should learn how to control his or her behavior. Arthur Combs claimed that the way a person perceives himself or herself is most important and that the basic purpose of teaching is to help each student develop a positive self-concept (Reyes and Dizon, 2015).

Both counseling and theories of learning recognize that every student has a unique personality and different set of behaviors that can influence his or her performance in school and the workplace context.

This is illustrated in the study done by Awadh & Ismail (2012) in the Saudi Arabian work context. The study revealed that personality traits and work-related attitudes such as job involvement and organizational commitment have direct positive significant relationships with employee's work performance, with the moderating effect of organizational culture.

The collective concepts, theories, and studies served as a springboard for the study's theoretical framework and paradigm.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Erikson's psychosocial theory. In Erikson's viewpoint, personality development occurs as one successfully resolves a series of turning points or psychosocial crises. Crises occur when people feel compelled to adjust to normal guidelines and expectations that society had for them but are not altogether certain that they are prepared to carry out those demands successfully.

Psychosocial theory claims that there are eight stages that everyone must pass through. Among the eight stages, the most important developmental task to solve in psychosocial development is identity versus role or identity confusion. Erikson saw identity versus identity confusion as the conflict during adolescence and the basic strength that develops in adolescence is fidelity, a sense of faith and commitment to a belief system. In the identity theory developed by Stryker (1968; as cited in Adamson & Pasley, 2013), identity is one focuses on the individual's integration of societal expectations regarding the meaning of occupying particular social positions or statuses (e.g., parent, spouse, employee) and the behavioral expectations associated with such statuses. This psychosocial theory plays a significant role in the personality of the respondents in this study-*Personality-based Counseling and OJT Performance of Students at Bulacan State University*.

Paradigm

Figure 1 is the research paradigm used in this research. The personal profile comprises of age, sex, and course of the respondents, and their personality profile, as measured by the standardized instrument, includes the following seven factors, namely: Agreeableness; Conscientiousness; Extraversion; Narcissism; Neuroticism; Openness; and Sensation-seeking are examined. The performance during the students' OJT is expressed in the performance appraisal forms submitted to BulSU by business and industry partners. This study sought to determine, if possible, the relationship that exists between personality and work performance as mediated by the counseling intervention program of the university.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used descriptive design and provided answers to questions associated with the research problem, obtained information concerning the status of the phenomena and described what existed with respect to variables or conditions in a situation. Using descriptive design, the data gathered were the source that provided a more detailed analysis.

In addition, it utilized descriptive correlation method to ascertain the magnitude of correlation between personality factor scales and work performance of student respondents of the two colleges of BULSU, Bustos Campus named CITBA and CIT.

Sampling Method

The study utilized stratified simple random sampling from the combined sampling frame of 684 graduating students from the College of Information and Technology and Business Administration (CITBA) and from the College of Industrial Technology (CIT) of Bulacan State University, Bustos Campus in SY 2017-2018. Under the Confidence Level of 95% and a five (5) Margin of Error, 193 respondents were chosen, 96 from CITBA and 97 from CIT.

Subjects of the study

Although the sampling originally chose 193, data cleaning only yielded 166 workable datasets: 81 came from CITBA, and 85 came from CIT.

Instruments

The Personal Data Sheet and Interview Guide

The study used personal data sheet to gather the respondents' personal information on their names, sex, age, college, course, year, section, student number, adviser, contact number, guardian's name, and address.

It used an unstructured interview guide during the counseling interview with the students to establish mutual acquaintances and rapport with students, and to validate the data gathered from the OMNI Personality Inventory Test. The interview guide questionnaire helped the researcher identify the student's attitudes towards his family, friends, schools, etc., which were not revealed by the respondent in writing. It was also an avenue of informing the respondent about his personality profile collected from the guidance office that led to the exploration of his personality and perceptual field. As the interview progressed, the researcher increasingly understood and assessed the respondent's special needs that had to be dealt with an appropriate solution. The researcher attempted to help the respondent in establishing realistic and attainable objectives for him or her to arrive at an intelligent decision and workable action plan. After the actual interview, the researcher evaluated the process for possible development of additional strategies and follow-up.

OMNI Personality Inventory Test

The OMNI Personality Inventory Test was used to have the personality profile of the respondents in terms of: Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Narcissism, Neuroticism, Openness, and Sensation-Seeking. The OMNI is a 375-item self-report personality inventory. The OMNI Test Booklet contains all 375 items and instructions for marking answers directly in the booklet. After the student respondents had completed the paper-and-pencil Test Booklet, the researcher entered the responses into the OMNI Software System. This software generated a report that contained the OMNI scores, and basic interpretive information based on the individual's responses that would be the foundation of their personality assessment. The OMNI Interpretive Report included tables and graphs containing the Validity, Normal, Personality Disorder, and Factor raw and *T* scores. It also included interpretive statements based on each individual *T* score as well as a list of responses to the Critical Items. The OMNI Software systems used the means and standard deviations from the OMNI normative sample to transform OMNI raw scores into linear *T* scores, having a mean (*M*) of 50 and a standard deviation (*SD*) of 10. Scores from the Normal and Factor scales can classify into one of five levels for interpretive purposes. *T* scores below 35 are classified as Low; *T* scores from 35 to 44 are classified as Low Average; *T* scores from 45 to 55 are classified as Average; *T* scores from 56 to 65 are classified as High Average; and *T* scores at or above 66 are classified as High. Scores from Personality Disorder scales can be interpreted at two levels: clinically significant and nonsignificant. *T* scores below 70 suggest that the respondent is not likely to have a clinically significant level of personality disturbance. *T* scores equal to or greater than 70 indicate that the respondent is likely to have a clinically significant level of personality disturbance. Validity scales are interpreted in a similar manner. *T* scores at or above 70 suggest that certain factors (i.e., abnormal mental states and inconsistency) may have affected the validity of results.

OMNI Personality Inventories employed two methods to measure its reliability. One method concerned the inter-item consistency of the individual scales, and the other method concerned their stability or consistency over time. The conventional measure of internal consistency is coefficient alpha. In interpreting alpha, it is important to realize that it is influenced by the number of items on a scale, as well as by the correlations among the items.

Preliminary evidence of the OMNI's validity is based on the application of several well-established psychometric methods to the field trial data. They include: (a) comparison of the Normal scales with other personality tests; (b) comparison of the Normal and Personality Disorder scales with a third-person version of the OMNI (i.e., OMNI Observer Version) completed by a spouse; (c) comparison of community and psychiatric patient samples on the Personality Disorder scales; (d) comparison of the Personality Disorder scales with a semi-structural interview conducted by experienced clinicians; (e) comparison of the correlations between the individual items of a scale and the total score of the scale with the correlations between those same items and the total scores of each of the other scales (Loranger, 1997).

OJT Performance Evaluation Form

In measuring the performance of the OJT students, the study utilized the OJT Performance Evaluation Form submitted by the BulSU OJT partners. The OJT performance evaluation form contains different attributes that are being measured to find out the level of the students' level of skills and performance during their OJT. For every attribute, there is a description given: (1) needs improvement; (2) fair; (3) satisfactory; (4) very satisfactory; (5) outstanding; and (NA) if it is not applicable. The attributes are their competencies in teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, professionalism, and productivity/resilience.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

The study primarily used the personality results already collected from the CIT and CITBA students by the Bulacan State University Guidance Office, Bustos Campus. While the CIT and CITBA students' work performance evaluations came from Bustos Campus In-Plant Office and CITBA Office, respectively.

There were two respondent groups. The group was divided for the collection of personality test results and OJT work performance evaluations, and for the implementation of counseling intervention. The first group took the personality test before they were sent to their OJT as a part of their requirements. On the other hand, the second group were given a personality test and counselling prior to their OJT deployment.

The gathering of data started in February 2018 until August of the same year. Table 1 below presents the statistical treatment applied on the data.

For the statistical treatment of the dataset, both descriptive statistics (i.e. mean, standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlation, chi-square, t-test) were employed for data analysis.

Table 1: Statistical Treatment of the Research.

PROBLEM STATEMENT	HYPOTHESIS	STATISTICAL TREATMENT
1. The Personal Profile of the OJT Students.		\bar{X} ,, SD
2. The Personality Profile of the OJT Students.		\bar{X} , SD
3. The Performance of the OJT Students.		\bar{X} ,, SD
4. The relationships between personal and personality profiles.	$H_1: \mu_1 - \mu_2$	H
5. The relationships of personality profiles and their work performance.	$H_1: \mu_1 - \mu_2$	r, H

Legend:

- \bar{X} = Mean
- SD = Standard Deviation
- H_1 = Alternative Hypothesis
- μ = Variable mean
- p = level of significance
- r = Pearson
- H = Kruskal Wallis

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Personal Profile of the Respondents.

The following tables show the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, and course.

Table 2: Number of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
17-19	105	63.25 %
20-22	51	30.72 %
23-25	5	3.01 %
26-28	3	1.81 %
29-31	2	1.21 %
Total	166	100 %

Table 2 shows that 105 participants were within the 17 to 19-year-old age bracket, 51 were 20 to 22 years old, five were 23 to 25 years old, three were 26 to 28 years old, and the remaining two were 29 to 31 years old. The data reveal that majority of the respondents were relatively younger, between 17-22 years old. This group was full-time students and might have received positive reinforcement and support in their academic pursuits. They took all the subjects offered for the course per semester to graduate in four years. Moreover, a few of the students who were 23 to 31 years old delayed their college education. Perhaps, they were part-time or working students that took them longer to earn a degree. The data would mean that the older group determined to finish a degree to apply for permanency and promotion. It was advantageous to them because they would have more life experiences, be work-ready, and be looking forward to it.

Table 3: Number of Respondents by Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	105	63.25
Female	61	36.75
Total	166	100

As regards sex, data reveal that 105 of the student respondents were males, while 61 were females. As observed from these data, technological and industrial courses appeal more to males than female students. This would mean that more males had a bigger interest in information and industrial technology than females. The BSIT courses at BulSU were more attractive to males than females. This gap means that amidst all the positive developments to promote gender equality in the Philippine educational system, there is still a great number of male respondents found in these fields. The realization of equality of male and female students in IT would perhaps not be easy in the context of existing cultural practices, norms, and perceptions that affect the lives of individuals and groups. According to Gumba (2016), women are naturally inclined to listen, talk, and facilitate conversations or attend to details like recording and budgeting. There are tasks associated with motherhood. Therefore, more females than males prefer education courses, nursing, psychology, communication, accountancy, management, and tourism.

To reduce the gender gap in IT courses, Wang, et al (2013) recommended that attention should give to addressing the contributory cognitive, motivational, and sociocultural factors, primarily by maximizing the number of career options that women perceive as attainable and compatible with their abilities, preferences, and goals. Otherwise, large numbers of technologically talented females will continue to slip through the cracks when their choices are restricted by cultural barriers, gender stereotypes, or misinformation.

Table 4: Number of Students by Courses

Course	Frequency	Percentage
BIT-Automotive	30	18.07%
BIT-FSM	55	33.13%
BSIT	81	48.80%
Total	166	100%

Table 4 presents the profile of the respondents according to their courses during the period of study. These three courses were BIT- Automotive, BIT Food Service Management (FSM), and BSIT. Data show that of the 166 students, 81 respondents belonged to BSIT, 30 were BIT Automotive majors, and 55 were BIT FSM majors. The data would mean that the reasons behind the students' choice to take up these three technological courses was their belief in their usefulness for their future careers. The study also revealed significant gender-based educational differences regarding all the study fields.

In this situation, 30 male students and no females were in the BIT Automotive course. This implies the nature of automobile troubleshooting is not that enticing for the opposite sex. However, the BIT Food Service Management course has more females than males-32 females, 23 males composed the BIT Food Service Management. It implies that technology-oriented courses, carrying a home orientation and context, enticed more females than males. The conventional wisdom that females are more inclined to serve the need of other people and having natural soft skills gave them an edge in choosing food service.

Many factors have an impact on the course choices that students make. Palmer et al (2017) used a best-worst scaling (BWS) survey to investigate the relative importance of factors to impact students' course selection decisions. According to their findings, students ranked *enjoyment, interest and ability*, and *perceived need* in their future study or career plans as the most significant factors in choosing courses. Moreover, Su et al. (2009) found that men preferred working with things while women preferred working with people. Indeed, to be engaged in studying IT courses, students need to have high levels of interest, skills, and desire for challenges (Wang et al., 2017).

Another significant issue is the quality of technical education, where the teacher's role is essential. Larmer, J., & Mergendoller, J. R. (2010) suggest that a teacher's role is a complex mixture of a learner, risk-taker, inquirer, curriculum designer, negotiator, collaborator, and teacher. It is to understand that the teachers' beliefs and perceptions are related to technological skills development. According to Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). teachers with increased confidence in teaching would likely be more effective at integrating technological activities, and increased confidence leads to better performance during instruction, which leads to gains in student learning.

II. Personality Profile of Respondents

Table 5 presents the personality profile of the respondents according to seven factors, such as Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Narcissism, Neuroticism, Openness, and Sensation-Seeking, and their descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation.

Data show the following personality factors with their corresponding mean and standard deviation, specifically Agreeableness ($Mean=44.11, SD=5.19$), Conscientiousness ($Mean=51.42, SD=6.94$), Extraversion ($Mean=33.61, SD=6.97$), Narcissism ($Mean=58.26, SD=7.60$), Neuroticism ($Mean=64.25, SD=8.21$), Openness ($Mean=43.2, SD=5.27$) and Sensation-seeking ($Mean=68.93, SD=10$).

Table 5: Personality Profile of Students

Personality Factor	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Agreeableness	44.11	5.19	Low Average
Conscientiousness	51.42	6.94	Average
Extraversion	33.61	6.97	Low
Narcissism	58.26	7.60	High Average
Neuroticism	64.25	8.21	High Average
Openness	43.2	5.27	Low Average
Sensation-Seeking	68.93	10	High

Note: SD= Standard Deviation

Data show that some students manifest the three personality factors- Narcissism, Neuroticism, and Sensation-Seeking that demonstrate a person's tendency toward abnormal psychology. It infers a critical issue in one's mental health.

Narcissism. In Narcissism ($Mean=58.26, SD=7.60$), data show that the respondents' Mean score on personality factor was high. This means the students are self-centered and have lower self-esteem than non-narcissistic individuals. The Narcissistic personality of the respondents showed an exaggerated sense of self-importance reflected in their arrogant-haughty behavior and excessive need for admiration and recognition. These students with narcissistic tendencies assessed themselves more positively than their peers assessed them. It is important to note that individuals high in narcissistic traits

encounter many problems, such as difficulty with interpersonal and professional relationships, and poor insight and self-awareness (Hampson, 2012).

Furthermore, narcissistic individuals seem to have a very strong armor regarding their sense of self. It is no secret that they view themselves very positively (Campbell et al., 2002). Because of this aspect of narcissism, narcissistic people ignore negative feedback so as not to let it damage their positive views of themselves (Morf & Rhodewalt, 2001). This may be an adaptive characteristic of individuals, having high scores in narcissism and not letting negative critique pull them down, but still being able to believe in themselves even in the face of feedback that contradicts their positive sense of self.

Furthermore, those with high scores in narcissist personality traits struggle to emotionally self-regulate, set goals, and motivate themselves to complete their work (Bembenutty, 2007).

Neuroticism. Data show that the mean of Neuroticism ($Mean=64.25$, $SD=8.21$) was high average. This personality factor is a dimension of normal personality, indicating the general tendency to experience negative effects such as fear, sadness, embarrassment, anger, guilt, and disgust. This means that the student respondents are prone to having irrational ideas, being less able to control impulses, and coping poorly with stress. Costa and McCrae (1992) describe people with high Neuroticism scores as shy, angry, insecure, depressed, vulnerable, and anxious. High scorers may be at risk of some kinds of psychiatric problems.

The study by Ijaz, M. and Khan, A. (2015) stated that Neuroticism personality traits are strongly negatively correlated with job satisfaction level of employees. However, a study conducted by Gonzales, A.V., et al (2019) about the respondents who possess neuroticism in their personality traits and borderline symptoms of major depression has satisfactory academic performance.

Sensation-Seeking. This personality trait of Sensation-seeking ($Mean=68.93$, $SD=10$) is classified as high. The data would mean that the students tended to underestimate the potential risks and dangers of specific activities. They are better able to remain focused on a task when there are distractions present than are low sensation seekers. This may have been likely because high sensation seekers are already used to engaging in multiple activities that served as a strategy to prevent boredom (Zuckerman, 2007). When high sensation seekers experience less physical pleasure, their satisfaction levels are also lower. Because high sensation seekers are shown to experience more pleasures in their social life and more daily satisfaction. One might conclude that high sensation seekers would also experience higher general life satisfaction (Oishi and Diener (2001). They were interested to participate more often in sports in general as well as in high-risk sports than did low sensation seekers.

Sensation seekers tend to be much less anxious in physically dangerous situations (Burkhart, Schwarz, and Green, 1978). Those high in sensation-seeking tend to have a larger network of friends. Sensation-seeking has been linked with extraversion. High sensation seekers tended to be more extroverted than low sensation seekers (Aluja, Garcia, & Garcia, 2003).

Agreeableness. Personality factors of the respondents in connection with Agreeableness ($Mean=44.11$, $SD=6.94$) reflected the low average range of the trait. This means that these students have an average acceptance of the people and the situation that they are in. This trait of agreeableness is seen when people avoid conflict, they are gentle and possess the tendency to agree with other people (Kochergina, Nye, & Orel, 2013). The respondents' average test scores on this trait are reflective of their desire to maintain respect for other people despite their domination. However, there are also occasions when they can assert their rights without resorting to hostility. Among the students, this is a very important trait since it is predictive of their job competence (Bao, Sun & Xue, 2012). Personality test scores also show that the respondents possessed a moderate degree of friendliness. It is seen when people avoid conflict, they are gentle and possess the tendency to agree with other people (Kochergina, Nye, & Orel, 2013).

Agreeableness can be the best predictor of the performance of employee personnel because the agreeableness trait contains attributes such as being cooperative, tolerant, and courteous with others. Mishra, G. and Dani, T. (2021) concluded that the agreeableness trait is a good predictor of job satisfaction. These findings were also confirmed by Agnes, M. et al (2017), as cited in Bodoso, E. S. (2019).

Extraversion. As regards Extraversion, ($Mean=33.61$, $SD=6.97$), data show that the student respondents have a very low level of sociability. This would mean that the respondents are reserved, unlikely to show warmth, and cautious in their behavior in social gatherings.

Krajenka (2018), as cited in Ehtashami (2021), stated in his study that people with high levels of extraversion ability have many friends and great relationships and communications. This confirmed the study of Bao, Sun, and Xue (2012) which found that students at the tertiary level who are extroverted tend to be competent in their performance. They need to interact with their classmates, professors, and other university personnel to accomplish academic requirements.

Extraversion has proven as a significant and positive predictor of employees' job performance, especially in jobs where interpersonal communications and interactions are high. It confirmed the finding of Nimmi, P. M & Zakkariya, K.A. (2017) in their study about personality traits as an antecedent of employability and the mediating role of job performance.

Conscientiousness. As regards the Conscientiousness level ($Mean=51.42, SD=6.94$) of the students, data show an average sense of responsibility and perseverance in their workplace. This would mean that they are purposeful, strong-willed, hardworking, and persistent, found to be conducive to OJT performance and attainment of academic honors and lower disciplinary infractions. The respondents need to increase their level of conscientiousness if they want to remain in their program.

Conscientiousness must be directly related to the OJT performance of students because of the natural attributes it possesses, such as being responsible, organized, well-planned, disciplined, and a goal achiever. In this regard, Summer, et al (1999), as cited in Knights, L. (2015), found that the Turkish military study utilized Personality-Related Position Requirements Form (PPRF) to determine that the most strongly relevant personality factor to the position of military officers was Conscientiousness.

Openness. In terms of Openness ($Mean=43.2, SD=5.27$), the respondents represented a low range of traits that may indicate a lack of acceptance of new ideas and concepts which are relevant in improving one's performance. Data would mean that the students tend to be conventional in behavior and conservative in outlook. They prefer the familiar to the novel, and their emotional responses are somewhat muted. On the other hand, people scoring high on Openness tend to be unconventional, willing to question authority, and prepared to entertain new ethical, social, and political ideas. Open individuals are curious about both the inner and outer worlds.

Van Dam, K. (2004), as cited in Nimmi and Zakkariya, (2017), suggests that Openness is considered an important antecedent of employability orientation. Openness to Experience includes active imagination, aesthetic sensitivity, attentiveness to feelings, a preference for variety, intellectual curiosity, and independence of judgment. And lastly, Openness measures the extent to which a person is open-minded. Openness to experience trait refers to personality characteristics such as curious, creative, broad-minded, intelligent, and imaginative. These characteristics lead individuals toward active participation in learning opportunities as training development programs (Barrick & Mount, 1993; Rothman & Coetzer, 2003).

III. Performance Level of the OJT Respondents

Table 6 presents the OJT performance ratings of the students as assessed by the industry partners. The ratings are grouped into four brackets.

Table 6: Performance Level of the OJT Respondents

Rating	No. of Students	Verbal Interpretation
96-100	47	Outstanding
91-95	87	Very Satisfactory
86-90	21	Satisfactory
80-85	11	Fair
Total	166	

Data show that 47 of the participants had a rating of 96-100% or outstanding, 87 obtained a rating ranging from 91-95 % or very satisfactory, 21 had a rating ranging from 86-90% or Satisfactory, and the remaining 11 obtained a rating ranging from 80-85 % or Fair.

Summary of the OJT Rating

Table 7 presents the average OJT Rating of the students. The mean shows the central tendency of the ratings is between 91 to 95. These ratings give a good picture of the respondents' performance with the industry partners. It is noteworthy that even though most of the student interns are very young-their performances are very high. This further means the students are friendly, reliable, and highly competent in doing their tasks.

Table 7: Summary Statistics of the OJT Rating

Statistics	Rating			
	80-85	86-90	91-95	96-100
Mean	93.52 (Very High)			
SD	4.65			
n	11	21	87	47

Note: SD = Standard Deviation; n = Number of Students

IV. Relationship Between Students' Personality and Their Age, Sex, and Course.

The following tables present the relationship between personality and personal profiles, such as age, sex, and course.

Relationship Between Personality and Age

Table 8 presents the relationship between personality and age. The Kruskal-Wallis H test shows no statistically significant relationship between the Personality Profile and the respondents' age, since $p > 0.05$, in all personality profiles. We can infer that age or chronological age is part of one's personality because personality is the sum of the person's traits. There is no observation so far that a personality factor is affected by age. Hence, the hypothesis that no significant relationship between personality and age is accepted.

Table 8: Kruskal-Wallis H between Personality Profile and Age

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	AGRE	CONC	EXTR	NARC	NEUR	OPEN	SENS
Chi-Square	3.001	.919	2.987	3.664	6.732	6.677	4.995
Df	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.558	.922	.560	.453	.151	.154	.288

Legend: AGREE=Agreeableness; CONC=Conscientiousness; EXTR=Extraversion; NARC=Narcissism; NEUR=Neuroticism; OPEN=Openness; SENS=Sensation-Seeking

Note: a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Age

Relationship Between Personality and Sex

Table 9 presents the relationship between personality and sex.

A Kruskal-Wallis H test shows no statistically significant relationship between the personality and the respondents' sex since $p > 0.05$. This means that sex cannot be a factor in defining the personality factor profile. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant relationship between the personality profile and sex is accepted since the personality factor has no sexual orientation.

Table 9: Personality and Sex

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	AGRE	CONS	EXTR	NARC	NEUR	OPEN	SENS
Chi-Square	.923	.335	.176	1.137	.008	0.943	.544
Df	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	.337	.563	.675	.286	.929	.330	.461

Legend: AGREE=Agreeableness; CONS=Conscientiousness; EXTR=Extraversion; NARC=Narcissism; NEUR=Neuroticism; OPEN=Openness; SENS=Sensation-Seeking

Note: a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Sex

The nature of personality profile and sex has no significant relationship in this study. Personality is the sum of traits of a person. It includes the biological makeup and the environment he or she has grown up. One's physical aspect is composed of the genes that are passed to him or her.

Personality and course

Table 10 presents the relationship between personality and course. A Kruskal-Wallis H test shows there is a statistically significant relationship between the personality and the course of the respondents, since $p > 0.05$. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between personality and the course of students is rejected.

Table 10: Kruskal-Wallis H between Personality Profile and Course

	AGRE	CONS	EXTR	NARC	NEUR	OPEN	SENS
Chi-Square	4.645	2.101	12.501	14.982	16.349	2.312	27.352
Df	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.098	.350	.002**	.001**	.000**	.315	.000**

Legend: AGRE= Agreeableness; CONS=Conscientiousness; EXTR=Extraversion; NARC=Narcissism; NEUR=Neuroticism; OPEN=Openness; SENS=Sensation-Seeking

Note: a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: course

A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that there is a statistically highly significant difference between some Personality Profile Factors and the courses of the respondents ($p < 0.01$), specifically Extraversion with $p = 0.002$, Narcissism with $p = 0.001$, Neuroticism with $p = .000$, and Sensation-Seeking with $p = 0.000$, all belong to BIT Automotive course. Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Openness have no significant relationship between the courses since $p > 0.05$.

Personality profile of Extraversion, Narcissism, and Sensation-Seeking tends to be self-centered and driven to competitiveness and personal achievements. These personality profiles are inclined to be an observer of the extrovert type of individuals. Assertive and loud and is the center of the life of a group of individuals.

They do not wish to be merely average and usually strive to accomplish more than others. Based on their development stage, the young respondents have a strong desire to prove themselves competitively.

Unlike the personality profile of Neuroticism, it tends to be anxious in social situations and feel that they do not fit in.

5. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERSONALITY PROFILE AND WORK PERFORMANCE

This study seeks to know the relationship between the OJT ratings and the personality profile. The data collected with the OJT rating and personality factor profile are shown in Table 11.

The table shows that the Pearson Correlation is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the personality and work performance of students is rejected. This strengthens the findings of several researchers.

Deepak (2016) concluded that personality traits and personal characteristics have a strong influence and bearing on the job performance of people managers, especially openness and extraversion are the most sought attributes in Information Technology.

Bodoso and Monge (2019) also concluded that the personality dimensions of Conscientiousness and Agreeableness are the strongest traits for the OJT students of the Colleges of Information Technology and Information Systems.

Klang (2012) found that Extraversion and Conscientiousness correlated significantly with job performance. Delima (2020) also found that Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Openness, and Agreeableness are positive predictors of employees' performance.

In their study, Judge, Higgins, Thoresen, and Barrick (1999) found that Neuroticism was related to the job performance of employees. This supports the study conducted by Gonzales, A.V., et al (2019), about their respondents who possess neuroticism in their personality traits and borderline symptoms of major depression have satisfactory academic performance.

In this study, however, it was revealed that students who display high levels of Narcissism and Neuroticism may perform poorly in their OJT stint. Unlike hypothesized, a significant relationship was found between OJT performance and personality,

Table 11: Pearson Correlation of OJT Rating and Personality Factor

OJT Rating	AGRE	CONS	EXTR	NARC	NEUR	OPEN	SENS
Pearson Correlation	0.062	-0.006	0.082	-0.151	-0.141	-0.015	-0.112
Asymp. Sig.	0.215	0.470	0.148	0.026*	0.035*	0.425	0.075

Legend: AGRE=Agreeableness; CONS=Conscientiousness; EXTR=Extraversion; NARC=Narcissism; NEUR=Neuroticism; OPEN=Openness; SENS=Sensation-Seeking

Note: * Correlation is significant at 0.05 level.

VI. Counseling interventions and OJT performance of students

During the internship program, counseling was offered through face-to-face interviews and counseling. This was done to find the validity of counseling interventions with the students' OJT work performance.

Table 12 shows that 68 respondents were counseled and 98 were uncounseled. The number of uncounseled respondents was higher than the number of counseled respondents.

Data reveal that of the 68 students who were counseled, 20, or 29.4% had an OJT rating of 96 -100, 35 or 51.47% had a rating of 91-95 and 13 obtained a rating of 80-90. Also, data show that of the 98 uncounseled respondents, 26 or 26.53 % obtained a performance rating of 96-100, 53 or 54.08 % obtained a rating of 91-95, 14 or 14.29 % had a performance rating of 86-90, and the remaining 5, or 5.10% had a rating of 80-85. It can be observed that the uncounseled respondents were more than the counseled ones. There is a total of 68 counseled respondents and 98 uncounseled respondents. There was a difference of 30 respondents that were uncounseled.

Table 12: OJT Rating of the Respondents and Counseling Intervention

OJT Rating	Counseling Intervention			
	Counseled		Uncounseled	
	No. of students	%	No. of students	%
80-85	6	8.82%	5	5.10%
86-90	7	10.30%	14	14.29%
91-95	35	51.47%	53	54.08%
96-100	20	29.41%	26	26.53%
Total	68	100%	98	100%

Table 12 would mean that even without guidance interventions, students performed well in the OJT program. Hence, even without counseling interventions, the respondents could perform well. According to Lucena (2015), some students perform well in their OJT because they have already developed appropriate work behavior before their internships. On the other hand, counseling interventions ideally help the students to analyze their performances and take them as their own.

Relationship between counseling interventions and OJT work performance

The statistical analysis of the relationship between the work performance of the respondents and counseling intervention is presented in Table 13. It was thought that the counseling given during the internship program would contribute to better OJT performance. However, data show that there is no significant relationship between the OJT rating and counseling intervention ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between counseling interventions and OJT rating is accepted.

It means the counseling interventions during the internship program did not affect students' work performance. This contradicts the findings of Canbolat and Hisar (2022) that there is a significant relationship between counseling interventions and students' internship program performance. The students, who had experienced counseling, had significantly higher theoretical and practical competence grades at the end of the internship program. It can attribute to proper workplace behavior, clear work expectations, and personal maturity.

The course becomes a negligible factor in doing counseling interventions for the respondents. It justifies investing in other guidance services. Instead of being reactive with the interventions, the guidance office can enhance work values through pre-coaching sessions.

Table 13: OJT Rating of the Respondents and Counseling Intervention.

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymp. Sig (2 sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.517 ^a	3	.678
Likelihood Ratio	1.511	3	.680
No. of Valid Cases	166		

VII. Recommendations for the University's Counselling

Based on the results, the following items are being recommended to increase the relevance of the university's counselling program to the OJT performance of the students:

1. Faculty members and the guidance and counseling office should closely monitor intern students that have high scores on Narcissism, Sensation-Seeking, and Neuroticism for possible intervention.
2. Enhancement programs that are aimed to increase Agreeableness, Openness. Extraversion may be designed, specifically, for student interns. Perhaps, school counselors could focus on the psychological well-being dimensions that need improvement such as self-acceptance and environmental mastery.
3. The university should have an intervention program or a student service program that would not only benefit narcissistic, neuroticist, and sensation-seeking individuals but also BulSU should endeavor to continue updating internship practices and training.

6. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study on Personality-based counseling and OJT performance of students at Bulacan State University gave a new look at providing counseling services based on the personality and the job performance of student interns. 166 participants were stratified and randomly selected from 684 enrolled students at the College of Information Technology and Business Administration (CITBA) and College of Industrial Technology (CIT) at Bulacan State University Bustos Campus. The research showed data on the age, sex, course, personality profile, and level of work performance of the student interns.

The personality inventory test was used to have the personality profile of the respondents in terms of Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Narcissism, Neuroticism, Openness, and Sensation-Seeking.

Findings

The findings of the study are summarized according to the statements of the problems stated in Chapter I.

1. Profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and course?

Of the 166 student respondents, 105 or 63.25 % were within the 17- to 19-year-old age bracket, 51, or 30.72 % were 20 to 22 years old, five or 3.01% were 23 to 25 years old, three or 1.81 % were 26 to 27 years old, and the remaining two or 1.21 % were 28 to 31 years old.

In terms of sex, 105 of the student respondents were males, while 61 were females. As regards their course, of the 166 students, 81 respondents were taking up to Bachelor of Science in IT, 55 students were BIT - Food Service Management (FSM) majors, and 30 were BIT- Automotive majors.

2. Personality profile of the respondents in terms of the following traits: Agreeableness; Conscientiousness; Extraversion; Narcissism; Neuroticism; Openness; and Sensation-Seeking.

The students displayed very high levels of Sensation-Seeking ($Mean=68.93$, $SD=10$), high average levels of Neuroticism ($Mean=64.25$, $SD=8.21$) and Narcissism ($Mean=58.26$, $SD=7.60$), an average level of Conscientiousness ($Mean=51.42$, $SD=6.94$), and low average levels of Agreeableness ($Mean= 44.11$, $SD=5.19$), and Openness ($Mean=43.2$, $SD=5.27$), and low level of Extraversion ($Mean=33.61$, $SD=6.97$).

3. On the Job Training (OJT) performance level of the students.

Of the 166 students, 47 of the participants had a rating of 96-100% or outstanding, 87 obtained a rating ranging from 91-95 % or very satisfactory, 21 had a rating ranging from 86-90% or Satisfactory, and the remaining 11 obtained a rating ranging from 80-85 % or fair.

4. Significant relationship between the students' personality and their age, sex, and course.

Relationship Between Personality and Age. Kruskal-Wallis H test showed no statistically significant relationship between the Personality Profile and the respondents' age, since $p > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant relationship between the personality profile and age is accepted.

Relationship Between Personality and Sex. Kruskal-Wallis H test showed no statistically significant relationship between the personality and the sex of the respondents, since $p > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant relationship between the personality profile and sex is accepted.

Relationship Between Personality and Course. Kruskal-Wallis H test showed there is a statistically highly significant relationship between personality and the courses of the respondents ($p < 0.01$). Hence, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between personality and the course of students is rejected.

5. Significant relationship between the students' personality and their OJT work performance level

The Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level showed there is a significant relationship between the personality and work performance of students. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the personality and work performance of students is rejected.

6. Significant relationship between Counseling interventions and OJT performance of students

Of the 166 student respondents, 68 had counseling interventions while 98 did not. The Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level showed there is no significant relationship between the OJT rating and counseling intervention. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between counseling interventions and OJT rating is accepted.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are made:

1. Technological and industrial courses appeal more to males than females.
2. BulSU students are different in several dimensions of personality traits. Specifically, they differ in terms of Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Narcissism, Neuroticism, Openness, and Sensation-Seeking.
3. Majority of the respondents had very satisfactory OJT performance ratings.
4. There is a lack of relationship between personality and age and sex, but personality plays a role in the courses of the students.
5. Personality directly affects work performance.
6. Counseling intervention does not affect the OJT rating of students.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are drawn:

1. Schools and higher education institutions should dismantle biases that prevent girls from dreaming of a career in the technological or industrial fields. First, by removing gender biases in learning materials. Such materials often portray male examples of professionals such as engineers and scientists while women are more likely to be depicted as teachers, nurses, etc. As people's aspirations are framed from an early age, it is important to have a variety of representations and role models.
2. Faculty members and the guidance and counseling office should closely monitor intern students that have high scores on Narcissism, Sensation-Seeking, and Neuroticism for possible intervention.

3. Enhancement programs that are aimed to increase Agreeableness, Openness. Extraversion may be designed, specifically, for student interns. Perhaps, school counselors could focus on the psychological well-being dimensions that need improvement such as self-acceptance and environmental mastery.
4. The university should have an intervention program or a student service program that would not only benefit narcissistic, neuroticist, and sensation-seeking individuals but also BulSU to continue updating internship practices and training.
5. Pursue research on other dimensions of personality types, mental ability, social skills, and leadership capabilities of student interns, and new strategies for our industrial partners to acknowledge more ways of achieving a high level of performance.
6. Conduct additional research that examines the relationship of counseling interventions with other OJT students in different disciplines.

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